

THE ROLE OF FICTION IN THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE AND ITS IMPORTANCE IN THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM

Zaynutdinova Dilfuza Shamsidinovna

Navoiy Davlat Pedagogika Instituti 1-kurs magistranti.

f.f.f.d. (Phd) Axmedova Zebo Jumakulovna

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Abstract: In literature, fiction refers to works that are defined by tales or stories that the author creates, invents, or makes up. Plot, characters, place, and topic are all common characteristics in fictional works. In works of genre fiction, these aspects might be literal, traditional, and formulaic. They can also be artistic, symbolic, and unstructured, as in literary fiction works. We can discuss the role of fiction in the English language and its importance in the educational system in this article.

Keywords: *fiction, English language, importance, educational system, books, role of fiction, fantastic books.*

Novels, novellas, and short stories are the most common forms of fictional works. When a literary work is designated as fiction, it means the written content is original and unique to the author's mind. This gives writers more creative freedom and invites readers to suspend their disbelief in order to accept the author's "world" as he or she has imagined and presented it.

In Mary Shelley's *Frankenstein*, for example, the protagonist uses his scientific knowledge of chemical processes and the decomposition of living tissue to acquire insight into the formation of life, allowing him to give life to a monster he created. As the reader accepts this version of fictional "reality," they get engaged in the novel's world and are influenced by issues such as natural rules against human meddling, loneliness, revenge, and societal responsibility. Novels that are well-known in the literary fiction genre include:

The book is a type of fiction that is both influential and significant. Novels allow authors to create entire worlds that readers may use as touchstones and glasses to learn, connect, and comprehend history, culture, and what it is to be human. The novel has the potential to be a powerful social, political, and cultural weapon for raising awareness, inspiring change, and giving voice to those who might otherwise be silenced.

Here are some examples of well-known literary fiction novels:

1. *The Great Gatsby* (F. Scott Fitzgerald)
2. *Giovanni's Room* (James Baldwin)
3. *The Handmaid's Tale* (Margaret Atwood)
4. *War and Peace* (Leo Tolstoy)
5. *Adam Bede* (George Eliot)

6. Ulysses (James Joyce)
7. To the Lighthouse (Virginia Woolf)
8. Beloved (Toni Morrison)
9. Crime and Punishment (Fyodor Dostoyevsky)
10. Common Examples of Genres in Fiction

Genre fiction comes in a variety of forms. As a result, these works usually satisfy the reader's expectations in terms of setting, characters, plot, and theme. Though some may perceive genre literature to be "formulaic," with predictable patterns, conventions, and conclusions, there is often diversity within genres, as well as overlap between them. The word literary fiction has no precise definition. Literary works, on the other hand, share some characteristics and are distinguished from genre fiction on a certain level, primarily in terms of what is deemed literary tradition. The following are some traits seen in most works of literary fiction:

- use of artistic language, including advanced and/or elevated wording and imagery;
- use of literary devices including symbolism, metaphor, allegory;
- Ambiguity in plot and subplots, with no set plot "formula" or conclusion;
- Narrative that is character-focused and driven;
- exploration of historical and cultural events and patterns;
- exploration of philosophical themes, including the human condition and the power of nature;

Literary fiction is seen as superior than genre fiction in some academic circles. Many works of literary fiction are deemed "classics" and worthy of academic study, and hence make up a large part of higher-education and literature curriculum. This, however, does not negate the intellectual or long-term worth of genre fiction. Many works of literature, in fact, can be classified as both literary and genre fiction. Popularity and commercialism are more closely related with genre fiction than with literary fiction. However, a work of genre fiction's wide readership or economic success does not always imply that it is of lesser literary value. Like literary fiction, genre fiction works tend to share certain characteristics, such as:

- adherence to established formulas for plot and character arcs
- use of more literal than artistic language
- spare usage of literary devices, including metaphors and allegories
- use of symbolism that is transparent, accessible, and overt

Despite the fact that reviewers and academics sometimes dismiss genre fiction as inferior to literary fiction, genre fiction is usually significantly more

popular with a wider audience. In reality, works of genre fiction are far more likely than works of literary fiction to become "bestsellers." Furthermore, while most enduring fictional works are literary, some genre fiction works also stand the test of time. Reading fictitious literary works is enjoyable for a variety of reasons, including pleasure, education, escapism, and even social interaction. Imagination, empathy, understanding, and growth are all enhanced by reading fictional literature.

Cervantes' novel is regarded as a major work of Spanish literature and a touchstone of classic literary fiction, influencing writers throughout history and across borders. Don Quixote investigates the meaning and purpose of fiction and nonfiction writing in relation to both the reader's expectations and the writer's implied responsibilities, as this paragraph illustrates. Cervantes' revolutionary narrative form, which resulted in the first modern novel, also opened the door for writers all over the world to explore fiction and imaginative expression in new, wide, and groundbreaking ways.

E.L. Doctorow's *Ragtime* He was buried alive in a grave and had to be rescued since he couldn't get out. They dug him out quickly. He exclaimed, "The earth is too heavy." His nails were bleeding. His eyes were covered in dirt. He was completely devoid of color and couldn't bear it. His assistant puked. Houdini sputtered and coughed. He had a bloody cough. They washed him up and returned him to the motel. The audience for escapes has grown in the over fifty years since his death. In their fictitious works, some authors chose to use genuine events, places, and even persons.

This line exemplifies how Houdini, a real-life historical figure, is treated as a full-fledged character in the novel, with the author attributing language and actions to him. Though Doctorow has dramatized and constructed the words, actions, and ideas of the historical personalities in the work, the balance between "actual" events and people as they connect with fictitious characters creates an intriguing representation of what is known and unknown about history for the reader. Doctorow successfully use literary fiction to challenge the reader's perceptions of the past, which in turn pushes us to consider how we perceive the present.

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